

Charting a Different Path Forward for Libya: The Role of Incremental Agreements

By Mariam Alsoudi and Misbah Omar | February 2025

Since the fall of Muammar Gaddafi's regime in 2011, Libya has struggled with political turmoil, economic instability and insecurity. The country has seen fractured governance, deep divisions between rival political entities, and a weakened economy marked by oil production disruptions, inflation, corruption, and fights over the distribution of resources. In addition, the country has suffered four civil wars, the most recent in 2019 when the General Command (also known as the Libyan National Army) attacked Tripoli. Although large-scale military clashes have not reoccurred since, foreign intervention, particularly by Turkey and Russia, has deepened divisions and tensions between Libya's two competing governments and legislative bodies, leaving key disputes unresolved and increasing the risk of renewed conflict. The failed national elections of December 2021 and continuing political dysfunction highlight the fragile nature of Libya's present-day stability.

LIBYA'S OVERDEPENDENCE ON OIL REVENUES has made its economy vulnerable to political disputes, with frequent blockades of oil facilities used as tools of political leverage. Mismanagement, corruption, and inequitable distribution of resources have fuelled grievances, particularly in marginalised regions like the south where communities face neglect and underdevelopment. These challenges not only perpetuate public discontent but also empower criminal networks, undermining progress towards peace. On top of this, the August 2024 crisis involving the Central Bank of Libya (CBL) highlighted the systemic weaknesses of Libya's centralised governance system.

Yet, the handling of some of these crises also offers a glimpse of how the country can move forward. For example, in the case of the CBL, instead of attempting a comprehensive agreement, a partial agreement was used to resolve the crisis. This and other examples highlight the potential of an [intentionally incremental strategy of successive partial agreements](#), with the prospect of increasing trust among key stakeholders and building positive momentum for broader, long-term stability.

To that end, this paper examines some of Libya's core challenges and the degree to which partial agreements may offer a more promising and realistic alternative to comprehensive solutions. By breaking down seemingly major issues into smaller, manageable pieces and steps, the approach may offer better scope for building cooperation and laying the groundwork for sustainable peace.

Setting the Context

Libya's instability is rooted in political fragmentation, economic mismanagement, widespread insecurity, and the weakness and inefficiency of institutions. These challenges reinforce one another, creating a cycle of instability that comprehensive agreements have failed to address effectively.

- **Political Fragmentation:** Libya's political landscape is deeply fractured, with parallel administrations competing for legitimacy and control. The Government of National Unity (GNU) in Tripoli and the Government of National Stability (GNS) in Benghazi both claim to represent the country, vying for authority over national institutions. This rivalry is mirrored in the legislative sphere, where the House of Representatives (HoR) and the High Council of State (HCS) frequently clash, further complicating governance. Centralised power structures exacerbate these divisions. With key institutions like the Central Bank of Libya (CBL) concentrated in Tripoli, a "winner-takes-all" dynamic fosters competition rather than cooperation. This marginalises regions outside the capital, particularly in the south, where communities experience neglect, underdevelopment, and limited political representation.

The failure to hold national elections in 2021 further highlights the paralysis caused by political fragmentation. Without mechanisms to bridge these divides, Libya is at constant risk of falling back into full-scale conflict, as rival factions exploit visible power vacuums.

- **Economic Instability:** Libya's reliance on oil revenues, which according to the World Bank account for over 95% of government income, has created an economy highly vulnerable to political disputes. Disruptions to oil production, such as the recent closure of ports due to disagreements over the CBL leadership, have cost the country billions. This dependence not only exacerbates regional grievances but also deepens public discontent over corruption and mismanagement.

The lack of transparency in revenue distribution fuels perceptions of favouritism, with Tripoli reaping disproportionate benefits while marginalised regions remain underdeveloped. Regional disparities are then compounded by the absence of economic diversification, leaving Libya heavily reliant on its oil sector and exposed to external shocks. High unemployment, particularly among youth, and insufficient investment in non-oil sectors like agriculture and renewable energy, further hinder sustainable growth.

Economic instability also manifests in social hardships, including rising living costs and inadequate public services, which disproportionately affect vulnerable populations. Inflation and a declining dinar have eroded purchasing power, while corruption and inefficiency undermine financial accountability. These economic grievances have empowered criminal networks and armed groups to exploit the disarray, perpetuating instability.

- **Security Challenges:** The proliferation of armed groups is one of Libya's most significant challenges. While some groups serve as local power brokers, others engage in criminal activities such as human trafficking and smuggling, operating with impunity. The lack of a unified national security framework leaves vast areas of the country vulnerable to violence and lawlessness.

Foreign interventions further complicate the security situation. Turkish and Russian forces, among others, have established significant presences in Libya, supporting rival factions and turning the country into a proxy battleground. These external influences undermine national sovereignty and reduce the prospects for a unified security framework.

Security challenges have far-reaching implications for Libya's stability. The absence of a cohesive security structure fuels internal divisions, displaces populations, and creates humanitarian crises. Additionally, the lack of security deters investment, disrupts economic recovery, and perpetuates reliance on armed groups for local governance. Without addressing this security vacuum, political and economic reforms remain elusive, trapping Libya in a cycle of instability and violence.

- **Institutional Weakness:** Libya has long struggled with the unchecked expansion of weak government institutions, a challenge that has significantly worsened since 2011. The problem has led to increased public spending, overlapping mandates, and a large workforce with many unqualified employees.

Political divisions further complicating governance, as influential politicians in both eastern and western Libya frequently establish new institutions and positions to empower and enrich their supporters, undermining the effectiveness of pre-existing entities. The result is overlapping responsibilities, entrenched corruption and patronage, and a fragmented system that fails to deliver effective services to citizens while draining state resources.

These challenges have taken a toll on Libya's economy and the quality of public services. The absence of a cohesive administrative framework weakens the already fragile institutions, exacerbates governance and security crises, and increases the hardships faced by the population. Moreover, the lack of a proper mechanism to select qualified personnel has led to the near-collapse of many public bodies. Addressing this requires reforms to streamline governance, improve accountability, and rebuild institutions to better serve Libya's population.

The Path of Incremental Agreements

Faced with these challenges, this paper advocates a shift from attempting to solve all of Libya's problems simultaneously to tackling specific issues incrementally. By focusing on manageable objectives that both sides may agree on, such as decentralising governance or establishing oversight for oil revenues, Libya can gradually build the trust and cooperation needed for broader reforms, while avoiding the high conflict risks associated with the pursuit of large-scale comprehensive deals. Examples of possible areas for incremental agreements include those described below.

Political Reforms

Decentralising governance through incremental agreements could help in mitigating Libya's political fragmentation. Negotiations could aim to establish a balanced framework for local governance that bridges the current gap between the national and municipal levels. This approach could empower municipal councils with greater authority over resource allocation and decision-making. By reducing the stakes of national-level political competition, such agreements could pave the way for a more inclusive and sustainable governance structure.

A parallel series of incremental agreements could focus on **resolving disputes between rival institutions**. For example, mediated negotiations between the HoR and HCS could help clarify their respective roles, reducing overlaps and tensions. The agreements could

also potentially encompass interim mechanisms to ensure that contested decisions, such as those concerning appointments to key institutions, are resolved collaboratively, building trust and cohesion over time.

Transparent and inclusive election processes could also be the object of incremental agreements. By negotiating piecemeal reforms – starting with local elections to build confidence and integrating the perspectives of marginalised groups – Libya could gradually restore legitimacy to its governance structures.

Economic Reforms

Negotiated frameworks for managing Libya's vital oil revenues could be economically stabilising. Stakeholders could leverage incremental agreements to establish externally-anchored oversight bodies that are both locally driven and internationally supported. These would be tasked with auditing and transparently reporting revenue flows, ensuring accountability and fostering public trust. By including representatives from Libya's key regions, such frameworks could promote equitable participation, enhance legitimacy, and mitigate perceptions of favouritism and marginalisation.

Other negotiations could focus on **equitable revenue-sharing agreements**. By engaging stakeholders from resource-rich and resource-poor regions, Libya could develop piecemeal frameworks that gradually improve the fairness of revenue distribution. These should ideally include timelines and milestones to measure progress, building trust among parties.

Incremental agreements could also be used to tackle **economic diversification in the country**. Negotiated partnerships with international organisations and private investors could focus on pilot projects in non-oil sectors, such as agriculture and renewable energy. These could create jobs and provide alternative income streams, reducing Libya's reliance on oil while fostering economic resilience.

Security Reforms

Negotiations and incremental agreements aimed at **reorganising and restructuring overlapping roles within the security sector**, including national security agencies such as intelligence services, the Ministry of Interior, and the Ministry of Defence, could be important for stability. The agreements could help establish a new framework that redistributes responsibilities and reduce overlaps, which often lead to armed clashes; enable the gradual integration and training of members of armed groups into security institutions; include international oversight, such as by UNSMIL, to ensure compliance and transparency; and integrate accountability measures to address human rights concerns and prevent abuses.

Foreign military interventions could be addressed through **piecemeal negotiations with external actors**, including dialogues to secure commitments for the gradual withdrawal of foreign forces, beginning with non-combat personnel. The negotiations could be tied to Libya's progress in establishing professional security institutions by providing mutual incentives for all parties.

Conclusion

Libya's challenges are wide ranging and deeply entrenched, but that does not mean its path to stability and democratic progress requires all-encompassing processes. To the contrary, by focusing on practical, implementable solutions and fostering multi-track approaches to dialogue, Libya's ability to break the cycle of conflict and build a foundation for a more resilient and democratic future can improve.

The international community, particularly UNSMIL, has a role to play in supporting these efforts. However, clear local leadership and ownership will be required, not only by local political and security figures but also by local **civic diplomats**. The use of pilot programmes and trial periods will also be important. The former allow stakeholders to test incremental agreements on a small scale, learn from challenges, and refine approaches before broader implementation; the latter, in turn, provide an opportunity to evaluate the impact of agreements within a defined timeframe, ensuring flexibility to adapt to evolving circumstances.

Decentralised governance, transparent economic management, and professionalised security institutions are needed in Libya. By moving incrementally through multiple partial agreements, the odds of their gradual realisation may stand a better chance of realisation.

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